

ANALYSIS OF INTELLIGENT CONTROL SYSTEMS FOR ELECTRIC DRIVES USING A MATHEMATICAL MODEL

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Abstract:

Objective. *The article is devoted to increasing the efficiency of regulation of a combined system of asynchronous motors with multi-link electric drives with a power of 0.25.....400 kW. The optimal method of a multifunctional control system adapted to control asynchronous motors up to 440 V is an intelligent control system. The control system allows the use of multi-link motors in manufacturing plants in existing machine tools and tracking systems.*

Methods. *A significant improvement in the quality of operation of a connected system of multiply connected electric drives can only be achieved by using dynamic models and synthesizing control laws that take into account the movement of a multiply connected system.*

Results. *Improving the intelligent control system in multi-link electric drives will reduce energy consumption by up to 12 %.*

Keywords: *Asynchronous motor, integrated system, multi-communication motor, adaptive control, associative memory, coordinates DQ control unit.*

Introduction. It is known that [1-3] control should be addressed when the complexity of the controlled process reaches a level at which it is necessary to take into account the influence of uncertainty on the conditions of the system functioning. According to the definition of control processes, adaptive control systems are divided into self-regulating systems, adaptive systems in special phase cases, and learning systems.

In the control of electric drives available at manufacturing enterprises, the intelligent control system is distinguished by the following indicators and features:

- improvement of indicators of speed control in the frequency range;
- reduction of energy consumption of electric drives;

Improving the regulation of variable parameters of electric drives by combining 3 or more motors;

- significantly expanded interface functions and increased efficiency;
- create an opportunity to analyze the basic principles of building intelligent control systems, methods and problems of implementing the technology of associative memory;

You can use the Matlab Simulink program to improve an existing control system. An important stage in the organization of a mathematical model is the consideration of variable dynamic equations in the electric drive.

Determine the frequency value generated by the oscillation using the following expression.

$$\omega_p = \sqrt{\frac{c(J_1 + J_2 + J_3)}{J_1 J_2 J_3} - \left(\frac{b(J_1 + J_2 + J_3)}{3J_1 J_2 J_3}\right)^2} \quad (1.1)$$

In this case a and b are variable coefficients, $J_1 J_2 J_3$ moments of inertia of the combined electric motor.

Results. The variable part of the mathematical model of a single-engine system is as follows (Fig. 1.2).

Fig.1.1. General power and double acting AC motor control.

1- Rotor-side VSC, 2- Grid-side VSC, 3- Rotor filter, 4- Grid filter

Using mathematical expressions 1.1. according to the figure (Fig. 1.2), you can build the following model.

Fig.1.2. Matlab Simulink software is an AC motor control model and control box

$$v_s = R_s i_s + \frac{d\psi_s}{dt} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} v_{as} = R_s i_{as} + \frac{d\psi_{as}}{dt} \\ v_{Bs} = R_s i_{Bs} + \frac{d\psi_{Bs}}{dt} \end{cases} \quad (1.2)$$

From Equation (1.2), for example, if the voltage drop across the stator resistor is small, the stator current will be constant because the stator is connected directly to the mains at a constant AC voltage; hence $d \parallel \rightarrow \psi \rightarrow$ equals zero. The last two equations show that it is possible to control the rotor currents dq using a regulator for each current component, as shown in fig. 1.3.

By relating DQ to mains voltage, we can construct a mathematical expression given the following equation.

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_a \\ x_b \\ x_c \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.3)$$

To help the controller in the program, the inverse conditions of equation (1.3) can be included in the output signal of each controller. The stator current and ω_p must be calculated according to the conditions of interaction, but this is simple and does not lead to an increase in additional difficulties. The check must be made in dq coordinates, but then the rotor voltages and currents must be converted to DQ coordinates. First, you can get the angle of the phase vector of the stator voltage, then subtract 90° from this calculated angle and thus get θ_s . In the control block diagram shown in fig. 1.3, the current rings operate with the rotor currents corresponding to the stator side and the conversion to the values shown on the rotor is done during the current measurement phase and before the generation of pulses. Using the above model (Fig. 1.3,1.4,1.5), the following characteristics can be obtained.

This, in turn, shows that the control systems are chosen correctly and the expression of the variable parameters in them has changed.

Fig.1.3. Changing the current I_{dr} through the control unit

Fig.1.4. Un voltage change via control box

Fig.1.5. Changing the current through the control unit

The main feature of the control of a multi-link motor drive system is the interaction of mobility levels at high speeds of the working body [1-5].

When building intelligent control systems, an increase in the speed of generating control signals is achieved through the use and processing of knowledge in the process of generating control signals [10]. By using the knowledge embedded in the control system, it will be possible to significantly increase the speed of calculating the control law, since the results necessary for this are not calculated in the control process, but are taken from the knowledge base. For example, in contrast to adaptive control systems, where the parameters of a controller with a certain motion trajectory must be calculated during operation, in intelligent systems, a set of controller settings can be included in the knowledge base and this knowledge can be used.

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